

Comparison of carrier gases for the separation and quantification of mineral oil hydrocarbon (MOH) fractions using online coupled high performance liquid chromatography-gas chromatography-flame ionisation detection

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Raw data compilation

Introduction

As revealed in the paper, experiments were run on a CHRONECT workstation MOSH/MOAH from Axel Semrau (Sprockhövel, Germany) and raw data were recorded and processed using the Clarity 8.5 software (DataApex, Prague, Czech Republic). This is the software used for MOSH/MOAH analyses using LC-GC-FID hyphenation in the vast majority of laboratories.

For convenience the raw data recorded are given in the *.cdf format. This is readable by usual chromatographic data processing software. It should be noted that due to the use of the flame ionization detector each chromatogram will on opening display a dominant solvent hump. As any analyst familiar with MOSH/MOAH analysis will know appropriate zooming in is required before further processing. The assignment of internal standards and analyte humps is possible via the information given in the article.

In addition to the original raw data in *.cdf format there are also versions having been processed (manually integrated) using the clarity software (*.prm format).

The raw data files and processed files are sorted according to figures and tables of the article. There is a folder for each table and figure in 7z format. Within each folder the files are unequivocally named to clarify the direct connection to the item in the respective table or figure in the article or the supplements.